

Review

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A critical review on the toxicological and epidemiological evidence integration for assessing human health risks to environmental chemical exposures

<https://doi.org/10.1515/reveh-2024-0072>

Received May 9, 2024; accepted November 27, 2024;

published online December 17, 2024

Abstract: Toxicology and epidemiology are the two traditional public health scientific disciplines which can contribute to investigate harmful health effects of exposure to toxic substances. Several frameworks for integrating different lines of evidence were proposed since 2011, evolving based of the emergence of new methodologies and approaches. Through the comparison of various theoretical frameworks for evidence integration, we examined similarities, differences, strengths, and weaknesses to provide insights into potential directions for future research. We identified several key challenges of the integration approach to be applied to risk assessment. More specifically, collaboration within a multi-disciplinary team of scientists, toxicologists, epidemiologists, and risk assessors, is strongly recommended to be aligned with key regulatory objectives and promote a harmonized approach. Moreover, literature search transparency and

systematicity have to be ensured by following validated guidelines, developing parallel protocols for collecting epidemiological and toxicological evidence from various sources, including human, animal, and new approach methodologies (NAMs). Also, the adoption of tailored quality assessment tools is essential to grade the certainty in evidence. Lastly, we recommend the use of the Adverse Outcome Pathway framework to provide a structured understanding of toxicity mechanisms and allow the integration of human, animal, and NAMs data within a single framework.

Keywords: chemical risk assessment; evidence integration; regulatory decision-making; new approach methodologies; harmonized approach; adverse outcome pathways

Introduction

The global production of chemicals has increased by a factor of 50 since 1950 and is expected to triple by 2050. This growth is driven by a number of factors, including economic expansion, technological advancements, and increasing demand for chemical-based goods and services. Currently, there are nearly 350,000 chemical substances registered for use globally, and 10,000 of these substances may be used in making plastics [1, 2]. Chemicals are essential to the global economy, however, they may have physical (e.g., albedo reduction, loss of visibility, greenhouse effects, contaminant transport, and resource depletion), chemical (e.g., photochemical smogs, acid rains, ocean acidification, and ozone depletion), or biological (adverse effects on human health and ecosystems, including biodiversity loss, carcinogenicity, mutagenicity, teratogenicity, and toxicity of equivalent concern) negative impacts at local, regional and global scale [1].

The Lancet Commission on pollution and health found that pollution remains responsible for approximately 9 million deaths per year, corresponding to one in six deaths worldwide at the global level. Over the past two

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decades, deaths caused by the modern forms of pollution (e.g., ambient air pollution and toxic chemical pollution) have increased by 66 %, driven by industrialisation, uncontrolled urbanisation, population growth, fossil fuel combustion, and an absence of adequate national or international chemical policy. Air pollution causes over 6.5 million deaths each year globally, and this number is increasing. Lead and other chemicals are responsible for 1.8 million deaths each year globally, which may be an underestimated figure [3]. Although more than 90 % of pollution-related deaths occur in low-income and middle-income countries, pollution remains a major global threat to health and prosperity even in high-income countries. Exposure to air pollutants is the largest environmental health risk in Europe, in which fine particulate matter and nitrogen dioxide exposures cause an estimated 253,000 and 52,000 premature deaths, respectively, in 2021 [4].

The toxicological properties and environmental exposure scenarios of only a small fraction of the chemicals on the market have been thoroughly investigated, while for the overwhelming majority of chemicals only limited or, in the worst case, no data is available [5]. This lack of knowledge negatively affects policy decisions, leading to ill-informed choices or, equally concerning, a complete inaction due to uncertainty [6]. Toxicology and epidemiology are the two traditional public health scientific disciplines which can contribute to investigate harmful health effects and doses of exposure to toxic substances.

In risk and safety assessment of chemicals, animal testing to predict human toxicity has traditionally received more attention than human epidemiological data, owing to the stringent adherence of toxicological studies to guidelines established by organizations like the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the International Council for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use (ICH) conducted under Good Laboratory Practices (GLP). However, the animal-centric approach has been questioned in recent years due to a number of shortcomings regarding performance, reproducibility, extrapolation to human, sustainability, costs and ethical reasons [7]. One of the main problems with animal studies is that they involve exposure to a single chemical at high doses, without accounting for the toxicity of combined, lower-dose, long-term exposures to mixtures of chemicals that are common in real-life situations. Some focused studies showed that traditional risk assessments may underestimate the health risks posed by chemical mixtures, especially at low concentrations. In some cases, these interactions cause the overall mixture to be hazardous at concentrations lower than the safety limits for the individual chemicals, amplifying their toxic effects [8, 9].

The use of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs), which comprise mostly *in silico*, *in vitro*, *ex vivo*, and *in chemico* approaches, can be used as alternative or complementary methods to provide information on chemical hazard and human risk assessment. Although they may have the potential to deliver sound, cost-effective, prompt and reliable information, their regulatory acceptance has not been established yet due to existing regulatory reliance on traditional animal testing methods [10].

On the other hand, the scientific discipline of epidemiology aims to study the distribution and determinants of disease frequency in human populations [11]. Unlike toxicological studies, epidemiological investigations primarily evaluate the risks associated with chemicals that have already been approved and released onto the market, focussing on human exposures that have already occurred. Although epidemiology studies examine real-life exposures in human populations, they can only show associations and cannot prove that a link is causative [12]. On contrary toxicokinetic studies, which explore how a substance is metabolized and eliminated from the body, are essential tools for evaluating exposure levels and potential effects. These studies provide valuable data enhancing risk assessments for individuals and populations informing public health policies and safety regulations [13].

Considering the strengths and limitations of toxicological and epidemiological disciplines, a proper integration can help to inform the process of chemical risk assessment. Toxicology can provide evidence on the potential toxicity of chemicals through controlled experiments, while epidemiology can examine real-world exposure and health outcomes in human populations, also targeting existing vulnerabilities and susceptibility. Table 1 shows the key aspects of the two disciplines, including their integration in risk assessment.

Several frameworks for integrating different lines of evidence were proposed since 2011, evolving based on the emergence of new methodologies and approaches (NAMs). In this critical review, we compared various theoretical frameworks for evidence integration, highlighting similarities, differences, strengths, and weaknesses to provide insights into potential directions for evolving the research approach.

Theoretical frameworks for evidence integration in human risk assessment

Although animal data from toxicological studies have traditionally received more attention than human epidemiological data, the integration of multiple lines of evidence,

Table 1: Key aspects of epidemiological and toxicological evidence, and their integration in risk assessment.

	Toxicological evidence	Epidemiological evidence
Key aspect		
Definition	Toxicology is the study of the adverse effects of chemicals on biological organisms. Toxicological evidence comes from laboratory studies, animal experiments, and <i>in vitro</i> tests that investigate the potential toxicity of chemicals	Epidemiology studies the patterns, causes, and effects of health-related events in populations. In chemical risk assessment, epidemiological evidence comes from studies examining the health outcomes of real-world chemical exposure
Data sources	Toxicological studies involve controlled experiments in which animals or cells are exposed to specific doses of a chemical. These studies often use standardized protocols and endpoints to assess toxicity	Epidemiological studies collect data from diverse sources, including population-based surveys, medical records, and cohort studies (long-term studies of groups of people)
Strengths	Toxicological evidence allows researchers to study the mechanisms of toxicity, dose-response relationships, and potential health effects in a controlled environment. It can provide valuable insights into the toxic properties of chemicals	Epidemiological evidence can directly link chemical exposure and health outcomes in real-world settings. It can identify associations between exposure to specific chemicals and diseases or adverse health effects
Limitations	Toxicological evidence may not always accurately predict human health effects because of species differences, variations in sensitivity, and the controlled environment, which may not reflect real-world exposures	Epidemiological studies may have limitations, such as confounding factors (other variables affecting health outcomes), difficulties in accurately measuring exposure levels, and ethical considerations that may prevent controlled experiments
Integration		
Hazard identification/ Exposure assessment	Toxicological evidence is used to identify or characterize potential hazards associated with a chemical. This includes determining the adverse health effects a chemical can cause and establishing dose-response relationships	Epidemiological evidence helps assess the levels and patterns of human exposure to a chemical. This may involve analysing data on exposure routes, duration, frequency, and population demographics
Risk characterization	Integrating toxicological and epidemiological evidence allows for a comprehensive assessment of chemical risk. Researchers consider both the hazard (toxicological) and exposure (epidemiological) aspects to estimate the actual risk posed by a chemical to human health. The Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) framework aids in structuring and integrating the evidence	
Uncertainty analysis	Integrating these two types of evidence also helps quantify uncertainties in risk assessment, essential for making informed decisions and setting safety standards	
Regulatory decisions	Based on the integrated evidence, regulatory agencies make decisions on safe exposure levels, risk management measures, and whether a chemical should be restricted or allowed for specific uses	

including NAMs, was recognized as an essential approach to improve chemical risk assessment. To comprise the current state-of-the-art, we critically searched literature to identify the main frameworks for integrating the evidence, identifying various proposals since 2011.

The first framework was published by Adami and colleagues in 2011 [14], who recognized the absence of systematic and transparent approaches to integrate data from the two disciplines to provide a unified view of an adverse causal relationship between an agent and a disease. They proposed a five-step process to conduct the human risk assessment, including the collection of all relevant toxicological and epidemiological studies, the assessment of the study quality and the evaluation of the weight of evidence, the assignment of scalable conclusions to the biological plausibility (toxicological) and epidemiological evidence, and the determination of the placement in a causal relationship grid. The authors declared some limitations of the

proposed model, encouraging further modifications to improve it. Two of the main limitations concerned the evaluation of the quality of the studies and the insufficient degree of detail to complete the two-dimensional grid.

Subsequently, Lavelle and colleagues [15] described a methodology for evaluating, classifying and integrating animal and human data in chemical risk assessment. In this methodology, the assessment of the study quality is also crucial and the authors provided a more detailed grid to integrate the two lines of evidence improving the transparency and objectivity of the process. More specifically, the authors proposed a classification scheme of four categories, A–D, to organize human and animal data based on quality, thereby addressing the limitation highlighted by Adami. However, similarly with the framework developed by Adami and colleagues [14], it was not possible to completely eliminate subjectivity in assessing quality and the risk assessment.

Woodruff and Sutton in 2014 [16] developed the Navigation Guide Systematic Review Methodology, a systematic and rigorous approach to research synthesis to reduce bias and maximize transparency in the evaluation of environmental health information. The inclusion of a detailed protocol drafted prior to undertaking the review, developed around a “PECO” statement [population, exposure, comparator, and outcome(s)], is one of key points of departure from previous framework. Also, the relevance of performing a systematic search for published and unpublished literature is strongly emphasized.

Lam and colleagues [17] applied the Navigation Guide Systematic Review Methodology for the integration of animal (mammalian and nonmammalian species) and human evidence for perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) effects on fetal growth. More specifically, they conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis for each line of evidence, and an assessment of the quality of the body of evidence separately. They found sufficient evidence of decreased fetal growth observed in both non-human and human species concluding that exposure to PFOA is “known to be toxic” to human reproduction and development, and demonstrating the effectiveness of the Navigation Guide in systematically and transparently reaching strength of evidence conclusions.

Later on, Hernández and Tsatsakis [18] emphasized the need for an integrated and systematic approach involving collaboration across various scientific fields, such as toxicology, epidemiology, exposure science, risk assessment, and statistics, to properly integrate data from these disciplines in evaluating the effects of chemical mixtures. Within this integrated approach to testing and assessment, Hernández & Tsatsakis [18] suggested the additional use of the Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) framework as a valuable tool for establishing causal relationships between chemical exposure and health outcomes.

More recently, the report produced from the SETE (Epidemiological and Toxicological Evidence Subgroup) [19] identified commonalities among toxicological and epidemiological approaches, including the identification of relevant literature, quality assessment of individual toxicological and epidemiological studies, quality assessment of the overall evidence, and integration of evidence using a risk matrix.

A general methodology for the integration of toxicological and epidemiological evidence

Chemical risk assessment faces several critical challenges and gaps that require action. One key challenge is maintaining

high data quality, which necessitates rigorous processes such as thorough data collection, validation, and quality control. Addressing these challenges is crucial to adequately safeguard public health from the potential harmful effects of chemicals as a precautionary approach often relies on robust data to justify preventive measures.

Through the collection and comparison of the different frameworks, we formulated a systematic and structured methodology to integrate both toxicological and epidemiological evidence, potentially enabling better informed decisions on the safety of chemicals. This work was conceived as a foundation for the development of an integrated systematic approach in human risk assessment to chemicals within a European granted project [20, 21]. Table 2 shows a detailed description of the proposed process, from the definition of the problem formulation to the periodic review of the evidence synthesis.

The first step of problem formulation should consist of a strong collaboration within a multidisciplinary team of scientists, toxicologists, epidemiologists, and risk assessors, aligning with key regulatory objectives to promote a harmonized approach. This collaboration allows the incorporation of the latest scientific advancements, methodologies, and data sources into the approach to address emerging concerns and ensures transparency and cooperation.

The literature review step provides a detailed description of the necessary phases to conduct a systematic and comprehensive review. A valuable scheme is suggested in Bilotta et al., 2014. “Key stages of conducting a Cochrane systematic review (CSR)”. More parallel protocols should be developed for collecting epidemiological and toxicological articles from various sources, including human, animal, and NAMs evidence. Transparency and systematicity of the literature search can be ensured by following validated guidelines, such as the PRISMA statement [22]. The registration of these protocols in registers such as PROSPERO (<https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospero/>) is strongly recommended to avoid research duplication. Also, the submission of protocols to scientific journals is useful in refining the search strategy and methodology before the conduction of the review [23], and allows for a more detailed description of the methodology without being bound to specific registry formats, increasing reproducibility and transparency.

The assessment of the certainty of evidence (CoE) is another key challenge of the integration approach. The adoption of tailored quality assessment tools is essential to grade the CoE. Regarding epidemiological studies, a new instrument to assess the risk of bias (RoB), tailored for non-randomized studies (NRS) of environmental exposure and health outcomes, was recently proposed to ensure a standardized, rigorous, and transparent evaluation [24].

Table 2: Outline of a general methodology for the integration of toxicological and epidemiological evidence.

Step	Description
Problem formulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Define the specific chemical or substance of potential concern and the main exposure route (inhalation, ingestion) and scenario (general population, populations at risk, occupational) – Clearly state the research objectives and questions that need to be answered by integrating toxicological and epidemiological evidence – “<i>A priori</i>” agreement on which early health outcomes (‘markers of effect’) are significant, enhancing the understanding of causal links through an integrated ‘system of evidence’
Literature review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Define the search strategies focused on maximizing the confidence in the causal link and the relevance of the effect for human populations (i.e. screening process filtering relevant studies, ensuring that only those meeting predefined inclusion/exclusion criteria are selected) – Ensure transparency and systematicity of the literature search by reporting on methodological steps in adherence to appropriate international guidance and protocols – Register protocols of systematic reviews in reputable databases to reduce research waste and bias and enhance the overall transparency of the work – Conduct a comprehensive review of existing toxicological and epidemiological studies related to the chemical or substance for ensuring that conclusions are well-supported and reliable – Identify relevant studies that provide data on exposure levels, health outcomes, toxicological mechanisms, and dose-response relationships
Data collection and risk of bias assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Gather epidemiological data: 1. Identify and assess the quality of epidemiological studies, including study design, sample size, data collection methods, and statistical analysis. 2. Collect data on exposure levels, duration, frequency, and population characteristics. 3. Adopt tailored quality assessment tools for observational studies to upgrade the contribution of critical human evidence in risk assessment – Gather toxicological data: 1. Identify and review toxicological studies, including animal (<i>in vivo</i>) and cell or tissue based (<i>in vitro</i>) experiments. 2.

Table 2: (continued)

Step	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Extract key study elements regarding study setup, methodology and (qualitative and quantitative) outcomes. 3. Evaluate the quality of toxicological data, including experimental design, endpoints measured, and relevance to human exposure
Hazard characterization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Determine the toxicological hazards (i.e.: the nature, severity, and likelihood of harm) associated with the chemical based on toxicological evidence. This includes identifying the types of adverse health effects and establishing dose-response relationships
Exposure assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Use epidemiological evidence to assess the levels and patterns of human exposure to the chemical. This may involve analysing data on exposure routes, duration, frequency, population demographics, historical and geographic data and environmental factors. Estimate the range of exposure levels observed in the population
Risk characterization and integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Integrate hazard identification (toxicological evidence) and exposure assessment (epidemiological evidence). Develop dose-response models considering toxicological and epidemiological data to predict the likelihood and severity of adverse health effects at different exposure levels. Use meta-analysis to synthesize data, measure heterogeneity and strengthens conclusions – Provide support to causality links observed in toxicological and epidemiological studies by considering the adverse outcome pathway (AOP) framework – Develop an AOP framework based on the epidemiological and toxicological evidence for the integration of human, animal, and NAMs data
Uncertainty analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Quantify and characterize uncertainties in the integrated risk assessment through statistical methods (e.g., confidence intervals, sensitivity analysis). Consider uncertainties related to data quality, variability in population responses, and limitations of the available evidence
Risk communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Communicate the integrated risk assessment findings to relevant stakeholders, including regulatory agencies, policymakers, and the public. Convey

Table 2: (continued)

Step	Description
Regulatory decision-making	<p>the confidence level in the risk assessment and any uncertainties associated with the findings</p> <p>– Determine whether the chemical should be allowed for specific uses, restricted, or banned based on the risk assessment. Include regulators in the collaborative team of experts to define a relevant research question to support conclusions. They may use the integrated evidence to decide safe exposure levels, risk management measures, and regulatory actions</p>
Periodic review	<p>– Monitor and update the risk assessment as new toxicological and epidemiological evidence becomes available. Adjust regulatory decisions and risk management strategies as necessary</p>

This instrument consists in assigning a low, moderate, serious, or critical risk of bias rating for seven items, which are confounding, selection of participants into the study, classification of exposures, departures from intended exposures, missing data, measurement of outcomes, and reported results. The RoB evaluation is one of the domains for assessing the CoE using four levels for quality of evidence (high, moderate, low, and very low) within the GRADE (Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluations) approach, which includes inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, publication bias, magnitude of effect, dose-response gradient, and plausible opposing residual confounding [25, 26].

Regarding toxicological studies, an example of a standardized method for assessing RoB for toxicological evidence is described in the Office of Health Assessment and Technology (OHAT) Handbook for Conducting Systematic Reviews for Health Effect Evaluations [27]. The tool describes various bias domains, including selection, performance, detection, attrition, and reporting bias. Another example is SYRCLE's RoB tool, which is an adaption of the well-established Cochrane RoB tool for human clinical trials [28]. SYRCLE's RoB tool is specifically tailored to animal studies and is comprised of 10 bias entries related to selection, performance, detection, attrition, reporting and other sources of bias. In addition, efforts are currently underway to develop and validate RoB tools tailored to *in vitro* studies, such as the INVITES-IN (IN VITro Experimental Studies INternal validity), a tool specifically designed for assessing the internal validity of cell culture studies including NAMs [29].

In our proposed integration process we also included the collection and the integration of the information provided by the use of NAMs to enhance the understanding on how a chemical may cause toxicity in humans [30, 31]. The effectiveness and reliability of NAMs in chemical risk assessment can vary depending on several factors, including the specific tool or method used, the quality of data, and the context in which they are applied. Their use in chemical risk assessment is recognized by regulatory agencies worldwide and the development of processes to establish confidence in the use of NAMs for regulatory decision-making are increasing [32].

Lastly, the use of the AOP construct, which is an effective approach to mechanistic risk assessment, provides a structured understanding of toxicity mechanisms and allows the integration of human data, animal data, and data from NAMs within a single framework [33]. Its reliability depends on developing and validating specific AOPs for the outcomes of interest. AOPs are increasingly used in regulatory risk assessment even if currently several limitations hinder their optimal usability and acceptance by the regulatory community [34].

Discussion and conclusions

Integrating evidence from multiple sources is essential for improving the quality of evidence-based decision-making for the safety of chemicals [35, 36]. A recent workshop on evidence-based methods to construct mechanism-driven chemical assessment frameworks revealed several limitations and a clear need for a rigorous framework to facilitate integration based on the best available scientific information [33]. Currently, no systematic, transparent frameworks exist to integrate different lines of evidence and generate a comprehensive understanding that no single discipline can achieve independently [18]. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses of toxicological and epidemiological literature have been proposed as a potential solution to support and justify policy decisions [37]. In this context, the general aim of this critical review was to summarize the existing frameworks and propose an integration process, from the definition of the problem formulation to the periodic review of the evidence synthesis, to guarantee an evidence-based approach for mechanism-based chemical risk assessments. However, limitations are inherently linked to both toxicological and epidemiological evidence.

Historically, animal studies have been the primary source of information for assessing the safety of chemicals [38]. However, extrapolating the results of animal studies to humans can be challenging, particularly when considering

chronic health effects as they may not always accurately reflect human experience. Traditional regulatory risk assessments often focus on unrealistically high doses of single chemicals, failing to account for the complexity of real-life exposure scenarios [39]. To highlight the limitations of this traditional assessment, the study by Vardakas et al. adopts a Real-Life Risk Simulation (RLRS) approach, focusing on long-term, low-dose exposure to chemical mixtures, reflecting more accurate, real-world human exposures compared to traditional high-dose, single-chemical studies. RLRS evaluates the cumulative impact of multiple chemicals over time, considering their combined effects, rather than the isolated effects of individual substances. Additionally, most experiments used to determine Exposure Limits typically focus on a single “stressor” (such as one chemical or environmental factor) in isolation which does not align with the reality that people are often exposed to intermittent sources of multiple chemicals at varying doses [40]. Moreover, non-chemical stressors such as socioeconomic and psychosocial factors can modify the exposure patterns but are frequently overlooked in these studies [41]. In addition to these inherent limitations, significant data heterogeneity, often arising from differences in experimental protocols, and a lack of sufficient methodological detail, pose major barriers to conducting meta-analyses in toxicology. These challenges limit comparability between studies and undermine the reliability of derived conclusions [39]. To address these issues, there is a need for more rigorous reporting standards and the development of statistical approaches that can better manage data heterogeneity [42]. Adopting these measures would enhance the accuracy, reliability, and applicability of toxicological research, ultimately contributing to improve risk assessments.

In addition to the limitations of toxicological studies, which can be mitigated with appropriate methodological precautions (e.g., use of physiologically relevant doses, application of multiple exposure routes, employing diverse test models), there has been a growing movement in recent years to reduce the use of animals in chemical safety testing due to ethical concerns [43]. In this regard, the European Chemical Agency (ECHA) and European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) act proactively to ensure that animal testing is used only as a last resort, providing regulatory expertise and investing in worldwide platforms on chemicals data [44, 45]. In turn, the use of NAMs, which include data from *in vitro* methods (e.g., cell-based assays), *in silico* methods (e.g., computer modelling), and omics-based methods (e.g., gene expression profiling), is rapidly increasing to replace animal testing. Results from these alternative approaches can be used for regulatory decision making by agencies worldwide because of their potential to reliably and efficiently

produce human-relevant information while reducing animal use [31, 46]. Aligning with this trend, we suggest that the overall judgement process should incorporate essential elements for establishing scientific confidence in NAMs, including fitness for purpose, human biological relevance, technical characterization, data integrity and transparency, and independent review [47].

Another critical point of the existing frameworks pertains to the numerical integration of data from different lines of evidence. Due to the impracticality of using a unified numerical value or metric, researchers often rely on descriptive and visual methods to represent causality or likelihoods clearly [19]. The use of tools that grade the quality of evidence and the strength of recommendations for both epidemiological and toxicological findings is largely recommended [18, 48, 49]. For example, the GRADE framework is a widely used systematic approach for evaluating certainty in evidence and the strength of recommendations [50]. Nonetheless, a definitive conclusion that integrates the certainty of both epidemiological and toxicological evidence may not be adequately accounted by a singly numerical measure in a graph. In fact, this would fail to capture nuanced considerations on certainty of the reported evidence. Therefore, it is suggested that more detailed descriptive considerations be clearly stated.

Finally, as advised by Tsatsakis and colleagues in their Editorial [39], we strongly recommend the use of the AOP framework to obtain a structured understanding of toxicity mechanisms and allow the integration of human, animal, and data from NAMs within a continuous framework. Once stated the research question, the existing library for the AOP development can be valuable tools to refine those existing or to select useful MIEs and KEs to be further proved or developed in line with the research issue.

In this context, a multidisciplinary research team has to define the problem formulation, identifying potential events which characterize the interaction between a toxic substance and an organism (MIE: Molecular Initiating Event), the progression of toxicity (KE: Key Events), including early key events at cellular level and later key event at tissue and organ levels (effect markers), and the apical adverse health effects at individual or population levels (Adverse Outcomes: AOs), (Figure 1). This sets the stage for a comprehensive investigation into toxic substance interactions with organisms. The certainty of evidence must be critically assessed to validate each key event relationship, strengthening the framework and identifying gaps to address the complexities of multiple chemical interactions. Adopting an AOP framework is well-suited for evaluating the combined effects of multiple chemical exposures, enabling the identification of molecular initiating events triggered by different pollutants

Figure 1: A view of the suggested framework for integrating toxicological and environmental studies, incorporating the AOP framework approach: MIE, molecular initiating event; KE, key event; AO, adverse outcome.

in real-world scenarios. This process can guide future research by suggesting pathways and tests to better understand chemical interactions, including cell- or biochemical-based tests for pathway elements. These can support the development of targeted toxicity testing strategies and identify steps in toxicity mechanisms needing further characterization [51]. Additionally, the potential interaction with other environmental and socioeconomic stressors is further considered in the epidemiological evidence conclusions ensuring that the findings are contextually comprehensive.

To conclude, our proposed framework highlights the fundamental importance of establishing a transparent and rigorous process for collecting evidence as a prerequisite for improve coherence when integrating toxicological and epidemiological data. Editors encourage peer-reviewed, pre-published protocols being considered a fundamental component of Cochrane systematic reviews. These protocols ensure transparency, consistency, and rigor in the review process enhancing the quality and credibility of systematic reviews [38]. While emphasizing the critical role of systematic review and meta-analysis in increasing confidence in the results, the organization of data into a centralized platform is equally essential. Such a platform

facilitates access to up-to-date and standardized information and incorporates blind access to ensure unbiased management of contributions from multiple researchers. Furthermore, it supports an efficient process for identifying and addressing data inconsistencies or feedback loops.

Research ethics: Not applicable.

Informed consent: Not applicable.

Author contributions: The authors have accepted responsibility for the entire content of this manuscript and approved its submission. conceptualization, G.D., N.L.; methodology, G.D., N.L.; writing – original draft preparation, G.D., N.L.; writing – review and editing, G.D., R.G., S.V., T.R., A.S., N.L.

Use of Large Language Models, AI and Machine Learning Tools: None declared.

Conflict of interest: The authors state no conflict of interest.

Research funding: Research described in this article was carried out as part of the ALTERNATIVE project (environment AL Toxicity chEmical mixtuRes through an innovative platform based on aged cardiac tissue model), which is funded by the H2020 programme of the European Commission (ALTERNATIVE Grant agreement ID: 101037090,

DOI 10.3030/101037090, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101037090>. The views expressed in this article are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

Data availability: Not applicable.

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